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PROBLEMS OF BUSINESS ACTIVITY DEVELOPMENT IN THE HOUSING AND COMMUNAL SPHERE

Abstract: *In this article, the author studied the problems of business development in housing and communal services, as one of the most important areas of economic reform in Uzbekistan, in particular, its importance for the socio-economic development of territories and sectors of the economy. He also developed proposals to solve problems such as high capital intensity and low labor productivity, an increase in tariffs for housing and communal services, a deterioration in the financial condition of enterprises, a high degree of depreciation of fixed assets, stagnation of the structural development of the housing and communal sphere, and so on.*

Keywords: *housing and communal sphere, capital intensity, labor productivity, tariff, financial condition, depreciation of fixed assets, stagnation.*

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ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ЖИЛИЩНО-КОММУНАЛЬНОЙ СФЕРЕ

Аннотация: *В данной статье автор изучил проблемы развития бизнеса в сфере жилищно-коммунального хозяйства, как одного из важнейших направлений экономических реформ в Узбекистане, в частности, его значение*

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для социально-экономического развития территорий и отраслей экономики. Он также разработал предложения по решению таких проблем, как высокая капиталоемкость и низкая производительность труда, повышение тарифов на жилищно-коммунальные услуги, ухудшение финансового состояния предприятий, высокая степень износа основных фондов, стагнация структурного развития жилищно-коммунальной сферы и так далее.

Ключевые слова: *жилищно-коммунальная сфера, капиталоемкость, производительность труда, тариф, финансовое состояние, износ основных фондов, стагнация.*

Housing and communal sphere is a technical complex of buildings, structures, engineering networks and equipment, as well as industrial, repair and construction production and maintenance. The result of the functioning of the housing and communal sphere is ensuring the safety and effective use of the housing stock, uninterrupted provision of housing and communal services necessary for human life, further increase in the level of improvement and sanitary condition of the territories of municipalities, and general comfort of living.

The development of market relations in housing and communal sphere is determined by the processes of sustainable development of business structures that are in the phase of active institutionalization. By institutionalization, we mean a complex multi-aspect process with a certain number of stages that ensure the formation of a wide range of entrepreneurship forms that fulfill their inherent target settings, ensuring the satisfaction of the population's demand for housing and communal services within a managed socio-economic system. All this contributes to the integrated development of the territory [1].

A specific feature of the current stage of economic development is the transition to the saturation with business initiative of industries, complexes and sub-complexes of the national economy, which include housing and communal sphere. In our opinion, business in the housing sector is an economic activity carried out by subjects of market relations in order to meet the needs of society for services, to obtain entrepreneurial income necessary for self-development and fulfillment of financial obligations to budgets and other business entities. The currently functioning business structures of housing and communal sphere, which distinguished by both interdependence and sufficient autonomy, and great diversity, divided into three groups [2]:

The first group includes resource-supplying enterprises and organizations that produce material products, namely, water, heat, electricity, the production and consumption of which either coincide in time or follow each other, and therefore enterprises cannot accumulate products and must produce it exactly as much as required in the current period.

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The second group includes housing management organizations, contracting repair, construction and maintenance enterprises, companies.

The third group includes multiservice enterprises and organizations performing work on external improvement, landscaping, collection and disposal of household waste.

Insufficient housing and communal sphere financing for many years has led to the fact that the technical condition of residential buildings, engineering equipment and communications is characterized by a significant level of wear and tear, high accidents, low efficiency of capacities and large losses of energy carriers. Despite the concrete measures taken in recent years, the problem of reproduction of fixed assets of housing and communal sphere has not been resolved [3].

Table 1. Features of the development of housing and communal sphere that determine the growth of business profitability

№	Features	Characteristic
1.	Industry attractiveness	Poorly developed competition and insufficient use of new technologies create conditions for generating additional income
2.	Stability in time	The industry will last forever, the volume of demand is quite predictable, the services are independent of fashion and have no substitutes
3.	Low elastic service demand	If an increase in tariffs leads to a decrease in consumption, then, as a rule, not due to a real decrease in the consumption of services, but due to a more rational attitude to services - the elimination of intra-house and intra-apartment losses
4.	Industry tariff regulation	Can lead to the creation of excess profits for firms if the price of utilities is overpriced
5.	Privatization communal enterprises and attracting to the private business sector	It is supported by the federal policy of market reform of housing and communal sphere, which makes it possible to hope for state subsidies and subsidies within the framework of targeted federal programs. It is interest that prevails for private business.
6.	Opacity consumption and payment volumes	Consumers of many utilities currently not provided with metering devices even by half. In this case, the

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		rate of consumption of services also turns out to be a tool for generating additional income.
7.	Level up trend life of the population	An opportunity is created for the growth of utility bills

One of the aspects of improving the management system for the development of entrepreneurship in housing and communal sphere at the municipal level is the modeling of managerial decision-making processes. In this regard, the simulation model of the housing and communal sphere' cost formation has developed, which makes it possible to make economically sound managerial decisions in the process of price formation. As part of its implementation, a phased selection of indicators characterizing the supply and demand for housing and communal sphere is expected; input of initial data, calculation of indicators and assessment of the results obtained; comparison of alternative options and selection of the optimal one. At the same time, the volume of subsidies and funds attracted to housing and communal services used as an optimality criterion.

The integrated development of business development requires the elaboration of an effective system for monitoring and diagnosing its current state in order to form a system of operational control, through the establishment of adequate feedbacks with the controlled object [4]. This requires the creation of an effective instrumental apparatus, the central link of which, according to the author, should be the integrated system of indicators for monitoring the development of entrepreneurship in the housing and communal sphere market, which he has formed. This system of indicators allows to characterize entrepreneurship in the housing and communal sector according to the main directions of its development.

Based on the above, we have developed the following conclusions and recommendations:

1. Housing and communal sphere are currently in a state of crisis, which is largely caused by objective circumstances associated with the transition from rigid government to a market economy, the government's refusal from the monopoly role of an investor, contractor and owner in the housing sector. The current problems are associated not only with the deterioration of fixed assets, but also with the institutional crisis of the country's housing and communal services system as a whole. One of the main ways to solve the problems that have arisen is the entrepreneurial reform of the industry, which will create a competitive environment and improve the performance of the complex.

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2. Housing and communal sphere of Uzbekistan at the present stage of development has a number of characteristic features that contribute to attracting business to the most promising markets for communal services. Disclosure of the specifics of the industry allows to adjust the mechanism for regulating entrepreneurship in the field of housing and communal services.

3. During the reforming period of the housing and communal sphere market, the contradictory nature of the implementation of state functions in this area was most clearly manifested, reinforced by the impact of systemic crisis trends in the economy. One of the tools for ensuring sustainable development of the housing and communal complex is the formation of a mechanism for the entrepreneurship regulating.

4. The ambiguity of the set goals for the formation of regulating tariffs system for housing and communal sphere and, as a result, insufficient regulatory and methodological support of this process led to serious systemic shortcomings in the regulation of tariffs at the municipal level. The developed simulation model of the formation of the cost of housing and communal services allows to economically select and make management decisions in the process of price formation

5. One of the fundamental factors in the business reform of the housing and communal sphere is the presence of adequate feedbacks with the managed object. The developed system of indicators and algorithm for monitoring the development of business in the housing and communal sphere market, within which the sequence of developing indicators, evaluating and interpreting the data obtained, is presented will help to solve this problem.

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